

ALL-Ready Project Deliverable 2.2

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

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Building Agroecology Capacity in Europe

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List of abbreviations

AE	Agroecology
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ERA	European Research Area
ERA-NETs	European Research Area networks
LL(s)	Living Lab(s) (Laboratory)
MS	Member States
RI	Research Infrastructure
SCAR	Standing Committee on Agricultural Research

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1. Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LL) and Research Infrastructures (RI) that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

1.1 Description of the Deliverable

The deliverable D2.2 'Building Agroecology capacity in Europe', is conceived as the report that will present the results of the mapping and analysis of funding support for agroecology relevant initiatives across Europe (FP7, Horizon 2020, HEU, etc.). The deliverable is related to Task 2.2.2 Mapping and analysis of funding instruments. It builds on the knowledge gathered in WP1 in which the overall conceptual framework for agroecological transition was defined. Further this deliverable feeds into valuable knowledge for WP4 (added value of the future network of LLs and RIs). The original deadline for the deliverable was M8 (June 2021) that was extended in agreement with the project coordination team to M18 (June 2022).

In the proposal of the All-Ready project it was mentioned that based on the methodology outlined in T2.1 (the framework of the mapping), this subtask will map agroecology-relevant funding

instruments under Horizon 2020 and FP7, along with rural and regional development funds, and describe in detail the functioning of the initiatives and (for Horizon 2020 and other current mechanisms) existing capacities. While national and European funding instruments were gathered and analysed in this deliverable, it was impossible to collect regional (and local) funding instruments all over Europe. This is due to several reasons. First, the person months that were foreseen for this task were already fully used by monitoring and analyzing the funding instruments on a European and national level. For instance, the enormous effort of building up a database that includes all projects since 2007 related to agroecology transition should not be underestimated. This large amount of work was also (main) the reason why the deliverable was delayed. Second, it turned out that valuable data on this geographical scale was almost non-existent online. Therefore, we considered it to be more suitable to focus on two geographical scale levels with all of the effort instead of adding very little information about regional fundings that would not at all cover all European countries. It also has to be mentioned that in the work of WP4 (added value of the future network), in deliverable 4.1. funding instruments are covered by conducting interviews, in which some might fall into the category of regional or at least partially regional fundings. There, interviews were conducted with funders from private and public sectors that give (at least some) input on their funding activities, hence, funding mechanisms are not completely neglected in All-Ready. As we saw there, interviews are most likely the only way to receive valuable information, but (as mentioned before) could not additionally be conducted in this subtask and deliverable.

1.2 Methodology used for Deliverable

Based on the methodology outlined in All-Ready T2.1, this report will:

- 1) **Map agroecology-relevant funding instruments** under FP7, Horizon 2020 (H2020) and Horizon Europe (HEU) and describe a functioning of the initiatives, policy background and existing capacities for Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe as current mechanisms.

Attention will be given to the analysis of how funding is mobilised to support agroecological research and innovation.

- 2) **Analyse the results of funding mechanisms** in relation to the extent to which they have led to, or are likely to, contribute to agroecological research and innovation initiatives and European level synergies.
- 3) **Analyse which funding instruments constitute actual drivers of agroecology transition** and feed into task 2.3 with the present deliverable: D2.2 'Building Agroecology Capacity in Europe'. The report will present the results of the mapping and analysis of funding support for agroecology relevant initiatives across Europe (FP7, H2020).

The task is done as desktop research with and discourse and data base analysis (mainly CORDIS) and a substantial retrospective element that is to identify agroecology (AE) relevant projects and programmes under the two previous FPs (FP7 and H2020).

In the context of agroecology research in Europe, the aim of the present deliverable is to assess effects of selected projects and programmes under different funding instruments, together with a wider funding policy landscape in which they were and are implemented. Additionally, specific information about the funding of LLs and the RIs will be asked through an in-depth questionnaire (online tool) which was developed through D.1.2 (inclusion criteria for organisations of AE transition) that is serving several deliverables in WP2. The research team primarily responsible for the deliverable 2.2. are AU (DK) and INRAE (FR), while ÖMKI (HU), FiBL Europe (BE), LifeWatch ERIC (ES) and AAFC (CA) are involved as consultation partners.

The information related to funding mechanisms and innovation initiatives relevant for agroecological research, will be analysed also through additional set of cross-cutting criteria:

- a) Funding mechanisms supporting multi-actor projects and process;
- b) Funding mechanisms geographical coverage (e.g. focus on countries and regions that were involved);
- c) Funding mechanisms focusing on sustainability. In the context of sustainability, attention is dedicated to the aspect of 'diversity' in the sustainable agriculture that is associated with practices facilitating and providing a direct support for the agroecology transition.

Throughout the analysis of policy documents and research initiatives the following practices will particularly be considered: co-creation, responsible governance, culture, economy, synergy, efficiency, biodiversity and climate adaptation, as levers for resilience (*Mindmap representation below*).

2. Agroecology related funding instruments

The creation of the European Research Area (ERA) in 2000 was one of the significant developments relevant for the EU research and innovation mechanisms. The ERA was created with an aim to overcome fragmented European scientific landscape associated primarily with scattered research communities and limited research cooperation across borders of the EU Member States (MS). The ERA was instrumental in establishing new mechanisms for transnational cooperation and funding by pulling together national scientific resources around identified thematic priorities. The creation of the ERA inspired new transnational cooperation instruments among the EU Member States and beyond, developed around Joint Programming and EC co-funded Public-to-Public Partnerships initiatives from 2002 onwards (e.g. JPIs, ERA-NETs, Art. 185 initiatives) (EC, 2009:3). How is this process relevant for building of agroecology research in Europe?

In the context of food and agriculture, it was primarily the EC together with the Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR), and in some cases also following a sectoral demand, that relevant thematic public-to-public networks were established (e.g. FACCE-JPI, SUFOOD2 Cofund, CORE Organic Cofund, etc.). The public funders networks have developed differently in the context of respective FPs and in the following sections we will focus on the FPs while indicating their main thematic areas and their capacity to support innovation, policy and socio-economic transformations with focus on agroecology. The understanding of funding instruments evolution is also a relevant foundation for understanding and planning agroecology funding mechanisms under the Horizon Europe.

2.1 Framework Programme Seven (FP7), 2007-2013

In relation to the ERA development, during the 7th Framework Programme (FP7) there was a persisting remark that 'overlaps between national programmes and EU programmes remain a challenge and more work needs to be done in better coordination and achievement of synergies of national, transnational and EU-programmes' (EU, 2015:76). Over time, for instance the ERA-NET transnational funding scheme proved to be one of the relevant

instruments in addressing challenges of the coordination with 71 ERA-NETs funded during FP6, moving towards 83 ERA-NETs and 23 ERA-NET Plus funded during FP7 with 52 ERA-NETs addressing topics that were not previously addressed (EC, Niehoff, 2014:4).

The FP7 mid-term evaluation further 'suggested changing the mix of funding measures and introducing more open calls in FP7-COOPERATION during the second half of the FP7. While top-down programming remained a key principle of FP7-COOPERATION, the relative importance of bottom-up approaches increased in HORIZON 2020' (EU, 2015:78). It also emphasized the core value of Joint Programming while highlighting 'the importance of opening FP7 to international cooperation improving the ability of European research and innovation to link up with other regions, markets and research and innovation agendas (EU, 2015:79). Consequentially during FP7, Joint Programming developed a new ERA-NET Plus instrument. This instrument has ensured that more countries participated 'larger average call budgets of €19 million compared to €7 million for the ERA-NET calls' (EC, Niehoff, 2014:2). Nonetheless, despite active engagement on creating the new transnational funding instruments that can be favourable to sustainable agriculture and agroecology transition, thematic coverage of the FP7 comparing to the present Horizon Europe had a very limited inclusion of the key concepts. In the Work Programme for 2013, agroecology is not mentioned, while relevant areas as sustainability, biodiversity, climate, organic and food systems, are only narrowly addressed (EC, 2013).

2.2 Framework Programme Horizon 2020 (H2020), 2014-2020

The FPs are complex instrument that reflect funding objectives and respective funding mechanisms, hence it is important to consider the philosophy behind their ever-evolving architecture. As an example, in respect to FP7, Horizon 2020 introduced a substantial change 'by **bringing together formerly separated research and innovation programmes** and a simpler architecture, centred on three pillars: 'Excellent Science', 'Industrial Leadership', and 'Societal Challenges' (EU, 2015:76). The change resulted in a working environment where the research activities were expected to feed into the innovation activities, where multi-actor cooperation was stimulated to further connect research performing institutions, policy and private partners' (EU, 2015:82).

In H2020 together with transformation where research is placed closer to innovation, 'Joint Programming and EC-co-funded Public-to-Public Partnership (ERA-NET and Art.185) have [...] been redesigned in a way that allows for more strategic cooperation between the national and EU level and to speed up this cooperation' (EU, 2015:76). In concrete terms, new **H2020 Societal Challenges (SC)**, particularly SC2 '*Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the Bioeconomy*' together with SC5 '*Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials*' have provided a platform for work on relevant aspects of the sustainable agriculture. Under the SC2, **agroecology is indicated as an example of agricultural system** together with organic and agroforestry, including multiple references towards sustainable agriculture and climate (EC, 2020a). The focus on sustainability, is taken further in the EC Work Programme on SC5 (2018-2020), where we further find that biodiversity, climate adaptation, overall sustainability and resilience are widely integrated in the calls (EC, 2020b). The agroecology is directly included, and its future relevance is indicated with a sharp focus on the research addressing climate change and biodiversity aspects.

The reform enabling jointly research and innovation will ideally be based both on a stronger transnational cooperation mobilising national and regional funding, and involvement of a wider range of partners. In H2020 there was an establishment of new 'Industrial Leadership' block that 'addresses the key logic of the private sector by focusing on innovation (rather than research), competitiveness and high leverage effects, while aiming to reduce administrative burdens' (EU, 2015:80). In the Work Programme the call texts were 'more open and less prescriptive compared to FP7 and there [was ...] a stronger emphasis on

impacts' (EU, 2015:83). These steps have paved the road towards more flexible funding mechanism in the food and agriculture area, where H2020 had total funding of approximately 77 billion euro and has maintained in continuity this funding level throughout its implementation. *How are these reforms more specifically related to agri-food sector research and innovation aiming at transition towards agroecology? What precisely it is meant by agroecology?*

The SCAR Foresight Report provides hands-on interpretation and definition of agroecology indicating that it 'is a more holistic way of designing and doing agriculture, so that it strengthens the environment and society around it. It includes improving soil health naturally, managing waste cycles efficiently, taking advantage of biodiversity and the ecosystem services it naturally provides. It is a science, a set of practices. It has social, as well as environmental, benefits' (EC, 5th SCAR Foresight Exercise Report, 2020:96). Agroecology transition is perceived as a pathway towards a broader transition of the agri-food system. It is given a multifaced role by taking further H2020 R&I agri-food objectives and making them more concrete in the Horizon Europe programme. It has a driving role towards agri-food system transition where fostering 'circularity, agroecology and bioeconomy in which strategies need to be aligned. Many policy areas are involved – economy, health, work and wages, digitalisation, fiscal - not only agricultural policy. This necessitates an emphasis on policy coherence' (Ibid, 2020:67).

2.3 Framework Programme Horizon Europe (HEU), 2021-2027

The SCAR Foresight Report had identified **three pathways towards a safe and just operating space, namely nutrition, circularity and diversity** while 'processes by which we achieve these three goals are all inter-related. Each implies **complex series of changes, or 'transitions'** in the language of foresight studies (EC, 5th SCAR Foresight Exercise Report, 2020:21,45). 'Furthermore, transitions are usually non-linear; and in complex systems, unpredictable major transitions may occur. For any desired transition, "lock-ins" – social or technical barriers to change, path dependencies – must be overcome. As a result, future innovation policies need to consider the whole system in which desired transitions would occur, and concentrate resources where constraints are stronger or opportunities are most promising. Foresight thus draws attention to the potential for change' (Ibid, 2020:112). **The future research is branded as transformative research** (Ibid, 2020:92).

What are specific funding instruments where the calls will be present? The foresight report also indicates that **agroecology as an 'approach to farming, already under trial around the EU**, needs greater study – yet it has faced resistance in parts of academia and industry, and needs support to break disciplinary barriers. Research now can help develop the theory, the practice and the ways to scale it up from individual field, to landscape, to a continent and the globe. We note the Commission has already started to move in this direction, with plans underway for a large, collaborative partnership and infrastructure on agroecology (EC, 5th SCAR Foresight Exercise Report, 2020:103).

The Horizon Europe has focused policy framework where '[r]esearch and innovation activities under cluster 6 ['Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment' will contribute to the objectives of the [European Green Deal](#) related to the [Biodiversity Strategy to 2030](#), the [Farm to Fork strategy](#), the [European Climate Pact](#) and initiatives under [sustainable industry](#) and [eliminating pollution](#), as well as the [long-term vision for rural areas](#), and the Sustainable Development Goals' (EC, Cluster 6, 2022: Web information). This ambitious scope of European Green Deal policy framework, favouring agroecology transition, is also reflected in the first Horizon Europe Work Programme 2021-2022 where sustainability, climate and biodiversity are the key concepts. Agroecology, together with organic farming and overall food systems, are mentioned widely in the description of the calls. The HEU is still to uncover its full potential in relation to the agroecology transition, primarily through launching of the new funding instrument European Partnership on Agroecology, its full title

is “Accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures” and its tentatively planned in 2023-2024 (SCAR, 2022: Web information).

3. Agroecology research and innovation initiatives

The analysis will focus on the extent to which research funding have led to, or are likely to, contribute to agroecological research and innovation initiatives and European level synergies. With our screening of EU funded projects we were trying to tackle several important questions. For instance, we were interested to see what is necessary for the development of relevant policies for AE transition? This aspect we hoped to address by an analysis of funding amounts allocated to different research projects, while consequently identifying the gaps among the funds spent. Furthermore, where there should be an emphasis in terms of research and innovation, as there should be openness in the architecture of funding mechanism for less identified and unknown research areas in order to be able to facilitate AE transition. We additionally were keen on identifying geographical aspects, and which (European) countries were involved and how much budget calculated for the projects in the different areas. Have some countries been more active and financially supported than others? Which categories of AE (crop farming, animal husbandry etc.) have been most present in these projects and which gaps could be identified? And finally, we wanted to identify if there is difference over time, meaning if there has there been a development within the last 15 years regarding how many projects have been funded and how much money as been spent?

3.1 Methods of data collection and creation of database

We decided to use the webpage of The Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS). It is the European Commission's primary source of results from the projects funded by the EU's framework programmes for research and innovation and lists projects from FP1 to Horizon 2020. CORDIS has a rich and structured public repository with all project information held by the European Commission such as project factsheets, participants, reports, deliverables and links to open-access publications. Therefore, we used this source to screen these EU research projects. As a first step we had to select specific target words that we would need to find all (or as much as possible) relevant projects that we consider to be able to foster AE transition. The decision of which words we chose was based on discussions within the consortium of the All-Ready project as well as through comparable analyses from scientific research studies. The target words that we finally decided to use did not only have to cover different ways of spelling of e.g. the term agroecology or agroecosystem, but we also had to keep in mind that these are rather young and not very well established terms and definitions. Therefore, we also had to add terms that might tackle agroecology transition issues, but maybe not directly use this language. The words we finally decided to use were: 'agroecology', 'agro' AND 'ecology', 'agri' AND 'ecology', 'agroecosystem', 'agro' AND 'ecosystem', 'agri' AND 'ecosystem', 'organic farm*', 'sustainable intensification agriculture'.

3.2 Analysis and interpretation of results from the data analyses

By using the mentioned target words, we found 295 projects that responded to our search. Projects that were not directly linked to agroecology (or similar topics) or they were related to other fields (e.g. fishery) were excluded. The screening period started with FP7 projects in 2007 and ended with ongoing H2020 projects that must have started before March 2022 when the search ended. From the almost 300 projects, the vast majority were H2020 with 242 (nine ERC) and only 53 FP7 projects. The overall budget put into these projects over the time period of 15 years was 1,376,480,904€, while the average budget per project was

4,666,036.96€. In total, 13446 months of work (1,120.5 years) were financed by the European Union, which is equivalent to an average of 45.6 months per project. Nevertheless, the number of funded projects was found to not being distributed evenly over time, with in most recent years an increasing number of agroecology-related and relevant projects funded than in the first years of the study period (see Figure 1). This could be related to the fact that terms such as agroecology are rather newly established terms, and therefore, several projects that might not have been caught by our search on Cordis. However, by using also target words that had been widely recognised since a longer time (e.g. organic farming, sustainable agriculture), we tried to also cover projects that were dealing with the same or similar objectives, but using different terms. In general, the terms of agroecology or Livings Labs were rarely mentioned in the project descriptions but still often and correctly being caught through the mechanisms of the Cordis search tool.

Figure 1: The barplots visualise the amount of Agroecology (related) projects that we found through the Cordis database, using our specific target words described above, for each year, covering all FP7 and H2020 projects from 2007 until today.

In 2008, only four projects were found, while the minimum number was two in 2010. With small fluctuations between two and 15 projects until 2014, a clear increase could be observed from 2015 onwards, where the number jumped from seven in 2014 to 36 in 2015. Since then, the numbers were relatively stable with a peak of 43 in 2019. This might have to do with the establishment of the mentioned terms related to agroecology, but also with the increase of importance and awareness of topics related to agriculture in combination with climate change, biodiversity loss and the problems of conventional agriculture in general. Here, agroecology can play a major role to booster the transition. In 2020 and 2021, the numbers slightly decreased which could have to do with the covid pandemic, or other indirect changes such as certain political decisions and changes, or the fact that the newest projects were not listed and updated in the database yet. Of the 295 projects, 214 were joint projects in which at least two (or often five or more) European countries collaborated, while in 81 projects, it was initiative(s) from a single country without European collaboration. In total, organisations from 39 European countries (also some countries from other continents were involved, but neglected here) participated in the projects. We listed all the participating countries for each project, but not each organisation separately (Table 1).

Table 1: The table illustrates all countries that were participating with at least one organisation in at least one of the projects of our search. We further show the absolute numbers of these countries

being involved over all the projects, and the percentages of each country that were involved over all European projects (e.g. Spain involved in 174 of 295 European projects).

EUROPEAN COUNTRIES	ABSOLUTE NUMBERS OF PROJECTS THE COUNTRY WAS INVOLVED	% OF PROJECTS EACH COUNTRY WAS INVOLVED OVER ALL EUROPEAN PROJECTS
Spain	174	59.0
Italy	168	57.0
United Kingdom	162	54.9
Germany	155	52.5
France	152	51.5
Netherlands	139	47.1
Belgium	120	40.7
Denmark	91	30.8
Greece	81	27.5
Switzerland	74	25.1
Austria	73	24.7
Hungary	71	24.1
Poland	70	23.7
Portugal	64	21.7
Sweden	58	19.7
Finland	56	19.0
Ireland	55	18.6
Norway	50	16.9
Czech Republic	40	13.6
Romania	40	13.6
Slovenia	37	12.5
Serbia	33	11.2
Bulgaria	28	9.5
Latvia	27	9.2
Turkey	26	8.8
Estonia	24	8.1
Cyprus	17	5.8
Croatia	12	4.1

Lithuania	12	4.1
Slovakia	10	3.4
Luxemburg	7	2.4
Ukraine	7	2.4
Iceland	4	1.4
North Macedonia	4	1.4
Malta	3	1.0
Russia	3	1.0
Albania	2	0.7
Montenegro	2	0.7
Bosnia and Herzegovina	1	0.3

Evidently, the amount of participation in the projects varied strongly among countries of Europe. This could be explained by the fact that some countries are much bigger than others, and therefore contain more relevant organisations, or have just obtained a higher budget and increased manpower. Furthermore, in some countries the political and societal will to transform conventional agriculture to agroecology is much further developed than in others. Initiatives from Spain (174 projects, 59%) represented the ones that have been involved in the most EU projects of our search, closely followed by Italy, the UK, Germany and France (see Figure 2 and Table 1). Nevertheless, also smaller countries such as Belgium or Denmark were involved in a relatively high number of projects. Most countries with lower participation were either rather small (Malta, Luxemburg) or came from central/eastern Europe.

Figure 2: The barplots show the percentages based on how often the ten most involved countries were involved over all 295 investigated European projects

In a next step, we tried to assign each project to a certain category of agroecology, for instance with main focus on ecosystem and biodiversity protection, reduction of waste and pesticides, bioenergy or rural and socio-economic development. Each project could also fall into several categories at the same time. We did that based on their project description and

objectives, in the Cordis database. In total, we built 13 categories. The category which we identified as the most commonly found was 'agroecology technologies and innovation', capturing inventions that can foster agroecology, followed by projects that deal with 'crops, fruits and vegetables' as well as projects about 'ecosystem and biodiversity protection' (Figure 3). On the other hand, projects that were linked to 'agroforestry', 'bioenergy' and 'food distribution' were identified with much lower numbers. One reason for these low numbers could be that these categories are often overlooked when it comes to agroecology as they are not classical 'farm land' categories, or are not a direct component of the food system. One hint why 'technology and innovation' was present in so many projects could be that it represents a category in which research infrastructures are heavily involved. Apparently, a broader range of people in the agricultural sector see an innovation in the agricultural system linked to innovation of technologies. Therefore, they strongly focus on this aspect of research.

Figure 3: The barplots illustrate the percentages of each AE category based on how often these are a main topic of the projects over the period from 2008 to 2021

4. Conclusions, observations, and future recommendations

The present work consisted of mapping research and innovation funding instruments under FP7, Horizon 2020 and HEU and describing the functioning of the funding instruments and evolution of relevant thematic areas that form the basis for agroecology transition. We have further analysed conclusions and impact assessments of the research programmes and instruments (e.g. ERA-NETs, JPIs, Art.185) and included them in the report. Attention was given to how funding was mobilised in the context of transnational cooperation to support research and innovation within the European Research Area. The need for three specific aspects emerged from 5th SCAR Foresight Exercise: long-term strategies, long-term funding instruments and long-term research infrastructures. We will focus on first two aspects and finally contextualise them under the agroecology research needs:

- The long-term strategies: 'The **shift from research to research and innovation** has been further fostered in HORIZON 2020 through the introduction of new funding schemes, the re-arrangement of sub-programmes, pilot and market replication projects, and industrial up-scaling. [...] While the recommended shift towards innovation and competitiveness was taken up by a broad diversity of measures, by now no explicit innovation strategy has been developed. This lack of strategic

approach – also in the broader sense within the whole setup of the Framework Programmes – is the basis for one of the key recommendations of this ex-post evaluation...’ (EU, 2015:77). The relevant response was provided by adopting European Green Deal Strategy encompassing ‘Farm to Fork’ and ‘Biodiversity’ strategies that are also central for the agroecology transition.

- Long-term R&I instruments. ‘One **problem with existing EU R&I programmes is their inherently transitory nature.** [...] [The] system has the virtue of focusing minds on getting specific tasks done, as determined by the Commission’s research policy goals. But it is not always fit for the chronic problems we face in food and agriculture: mitigating climate change, improving nutrition, boosting diversity, turning to agroecology – these are all goals that will live with us for years to come. They require more long-term networks and infrastructures, that live beyond the usual EU budgetary cycles. Long-term networks keep relations alive among the participants. They encourage more attention to communications, implementation and impact’ (EC, 5th SCAR Foresight Exercise Report, 2020:103). The issue touches upon the transformation of Joint Programming instruments, where for instance JPI and ERA-NET funding mechanism, were phased out and agri-food related transnational cooperation in the HEU is envisaged through new European Partnership instruments that are currently developed. It would be important that in the HEU new funding instruments are built upon the existing values and practices developed throughout two decades of the Joint Programming implementation that ‘delivered a wealth of intangible results such as the establishment of new relationships and networks between funding organisations’ (EU, 2009:3). This will be one of prerequisites for the success of agroecology transition and relevant funding mechanisms.

Overall, our analyses showed that there are (expected) differences over time, space and AE categories. These differences could or should be analysed and interpreted carefully to make sure the transition process is fostered all across Europe and that funds are spent wisely and mistakes are not repeated. In the best case, policy-makers could receive recommendations on how to ensure to work towards the right direction. For instance, research and innovation gaps should be identified. As mentioned above, this category plays an important role in the majority of all projects, but often is not necessarily targeting AE transition. Here, innovation projects could have a stronger focus on agroecology transition. Also, the research community needs to have a stronger focus on this aim. Furthermore, despite the capacities and sizes of countries strongly vary, the geographical diversity should be highlighted. As several countries are barely involved in the projects (especially in Central-Eastern Europe), it has to be ensured that the diversity does not just end within each single project, but really effectively spreads over the whole continent. Here, solutions have to be found, especially regarding finances/funding, expertise and capacities. Additionally, there is a big discrepancy regarding the various categories of agroecology that are present within the projects. That is understandable on one hand, as e.g. crop production plays a bigger role within the food system than agroforestry. Nevertheless, it is important that every aspect of agroecology is valued and visible within the funding business plan as it is a waste of resources to financially cover several similar projects about comparable problems while other aspects are completely out of the focus. Agroecology has a wide range of facets. This should be visible and picture a diversity – on the level of geography, but also agroecological categories and practices in the future.

References

European Commission. FP6 ERA-NET Study. Summary of the Impact Assessment of the ERA-NET scheme under the Sixth Framework Programme Commitment and Coherence essential ingredients for success in science and innovation. June 2009.

European Commission. FP7, Work Programme 2013. Theme 2: Food, agriculture and fisheries, and biotechnology. European Commission Decision C (2013) 3953 of 2 June 2013.

European Commission, Jörg Niehoff. The ERA-NET scheme from FP6 to Horizon 2020. Report on ERA-NETs, their calls and the experiences from the first call under Horizon 2020. October 2014.

European Commission. Commitment and Coherence essential ingredients for success in science and innovation. The High Level Expert Group Ex-Post Evaluation of the 7th EU Framework Programme (2007-2013). November 2015.

European Commission. H2020, Work Programme 2018-2020, 9. Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research and the bioeconomy Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials. European Commission Decision C (2020)6320 of 17 September 2020 (a).

European Commission. H2020, Work Programme 2018-2020, 12. Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials. European Commission Decision C(2020)6320 of 17 September 2020 (b).

European Commission. Horizon Europe, Work Programme 2021-2022, 9. Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment. European Commission Decision C(2022)2975 of 10 May 2022.

European Commission. Horizon Europe, Cluster 6: Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment. Policy, strategy, how to apply and work programmes. June, 2022: https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/cluster-6-food-bioeconomy-natural-resources-agriculture-and-environment_en

Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR), Strategic Working Group on Agroecology (SCAR-AE). June, 2022: <https://scar-europe.org/index.php/documents>